

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE
TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS.

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Annotation: This article discusses the measures taken to develop the professional competence of future teachers of technological education.

Key words: pedagogical technology , scientific research , professional ability , pedagogical technologies , modern educational technologies .

Today, a continuous education system aimed at ensuring the effective organization of the process of training competent individuals and qualified specialists has been formed. In order to improve the effectiveness of the continuous education system, it is important to organize the activities of higher education institutions on the basis of the educational process with a new content, based on advanced, democratic and humanitarian ideas. Formation of continuous education system, updating of educational content are the main goals of the reforms in the field of education. Achieving this important goal requires a new approach to the organization of the educational process. After gaining independence, as a leading stage of the continuous education system, it is considered appropriate to search for factors that serve to increase the effectiveness of the pedagogical process in higher education institutions, to accelerate practical efforts to consistently implement the pedagogical technologies found to be acceptable factors. In the educational system, the process of educating a person who is competent, who thinks independently and consciously carries out methodical activities, who can quickly adapt to the profession of a technology teacher, has a unique place. One of the main goals of the comprehensive reforms carried out in the continuous education system in our country today is to fully support young people in acquiring deep knowledge, realizing their talents, and at the same time forming their skills to prepare them for independent life. is one of the priority directions of the education system. It is no secret that we are not able to provide future technological education teachers with life skills, creative thinking and life professional skills. At the same time, it was determined that various approaches to increase the effectiveness of training future technology teachers, the mechanism of ensuring the effectiveness of the "Technology Teaching Methodology" educational subject is insufficient. By looking at the science of "Technological Education" as a vital need for future technological education teachers and youth education, we not only prevent pupils and students from suffering from diseases of impatience and laziness, but also prepare them to become the owner of a certain profession in the future. we need to create the ground. Every year, thousands of students and young people graduate from about ten thousand general secondary schools operating in our country, and 25-30% of them continue to study at higher educational institutions. . 70-75 percent of graduating youth start their work or learn a trade in professional educational institutions. requires radical revision and improvement based on education programs. Many pedagogues are also conducting technology classes today using pedagogical technologies. Because the subject-pedagogical system of pedagogical technology consists of proving its conceptual foundations, clearly setting the goal, formulating the obtained results, choosing and structuring the educational material, choosing the pedagogical model, until their implementation, and designing

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them to evaluate their alternative and efficiency level, and the lesson serves for the effect. Taking into account the long-term scenarios of the country's development, there is a need to develop innovations and introduce them to the construction of the state and society, as well as to develop priority and promising directions of scientific research and advanced technologies that ensure the development of society and the state. Currently, consistent introduction of modern educational technologies in the training of agrarian specialists remains a vital necessity. A number of scientific works have been devoted to the study of the problem of education of the teacher's professional competence. However, the interest of scientists in various aspects and aspects of this problem is not decreasing, which indicates the special importance and relevance of the modernization and development of the continuous pedagogical education system at the current stage. Person-oriented teaching is a process that takes into account the student's personal characteristics, interests, abilities and opportunities, and is aimed at the effective use of advanced pedagogical and information technologies in the development of the student's personality. Therefore, differentiation and individualization of teaching serve as the main principles of introducing person-oriented education. In that case, the professionalism of pedagogical activity, in the opinion of N.V. Kuzmina, is understandable when he says that "the elements of scientific research are included for the purposes of control, the measurement of its productivity." In this case, productivity is defined as a system of pedagogically appropriate actions that ensures the achievement of the desired final result for all or the majority of students within the time allocated to the educational process related to solving pedagogical tasks. In conclusion, improving the professional competence of future technology education teachers, forming their knowledge, skills and qualifications, using new methods, innovative technologies, and interactive methods to fundamentally improve skills is a very urgent issue today. We, teachers of technology education, should not be indifferent to this. I think that we should look for new ways to improve professional knowledge, professional ability and professional skills in the formation of the young generation. In order to ensure the large-scale social and economic development of our country, competitive specialists with high professional skills are of primary importance. For this purpose, in the following years, the education system in our republic will be fundamentally reformed, and activities will be carried out with high efficiency in various sectors of the national economy. Great attention is being paid to the training of specialists who can show. In this regard, the need to use the experiences of developed countries in our country has become a priority issue. The creation of new textbooks using the Finnish educational system is a clear manifestation of this. In this case, the methods are updated, in particular, STEAM, SMART, and international assessment criteria PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS. In order to improve the professional competence of teachers, it is necessary to implement the effective use of STEAM and SMART system methods. Using these methods, textbooks and educational literature will help us to achieve our goals. Also, STEAM PARKS and SMART rooms are being organized in educational institutions. When creating the concept of preparing a teacher for innovative activities, systematic, reflexive-active, individual-creative approaches that ensure the design and implementation of the entire process of teacher personality formation are used as a basis.

For example, in terms of a systematic approach, all links of pedagogical education should maximally stimulate the emergence of all components of innovative activity in their entirety.

The implementation of the reflexive-active approach implies the development of the teacher's ability to enter into an active research position in order to critically analyze, reflect and

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evaluate the effectiveness of the teacher in relation to his own activity and the development of the student's personality as a subject of activity.

The individual-creative approach brings the identification and formation of creative individuality in the teacher, the development of innovative consciousness in him to the personal level, which provides unique technology of activity.

In short, starting the innovative activities of the pedagogue will clarify his views on the perception of objective reality. The problem of preparing a teacher for innovative activities can be expressed as a system that includes several interrelated and functional components that are subject to certain goals.

The innovative readiness of the future teacher is his theoretical, practical and psychological-physiological level of mastering the full essence of pedagogical innovation in the conditions of continuous education. As a result of the pedagogical system, such preparation should help students to form a whole set of knowledge and skills in certain subjects, general professional activities based on ensuring the integrity of theory and practice, educating conscientious attitude to educational work, and developing creative activity.

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